

THE ROLE OF GRAPHIC ORGANIZERS IN TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY

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Abstract: A graphic organizer is what helps to organize information on a sheet of paper in order to improve understanding, assimilation, memorization, and analysis of educational material. DL contributes to the process of organized learning, helps to meet the educational needs of students in achieving learning goals. Graphic organizers are visual communication tools that use visual means of expressing content. They are the best way for students to organize their thoughts, comprehend information through visualization, and provide structure for short and long term memory. As a didactic tool that performs illustrative, communicative and cognitive functions, graphic organizers are used not only as a carrier of information, but also to support the activities of students in planning educational projects, solving problems, making decisions, conducting research and evaluating.

Key words: graphic organizers, function, didactic, communication, active methods, efficiency, criteria.

Graphic organizers are anything that somehow helps to organize information on a piece of paper (or computer screen) in order to improve its memorization, assimilation, analysis or application. Or, in the language of definitions, visual communication tools that use visual means of expressing content. They play an increasing role in the process of organized learning and can be successfully used in self-education and formative assessment. Each of us used the simplest “graphic organizer” when we divided a sheet of paper into two parts, listing the pluses on the left and the minuses of this or that phenomenon on the right. Next step: divide the same sheet into four parts. You can, of course, not use any graphics, but when the lists and numbers are next to each other, the comparison goes faster. Most graphic organizers present information as a convincing visual picture and allow the mind to “see” hidden patterns and relationships. The most effective active methods in the lessons of all language and literature are graphic organizers, which we will well on in more detail. In the process of visualizing information, the student thinks, comprehends, skips information through itself, presenting it in a visual-conceptual way. Students master the methods of searching, confirming, systematizing and arguing information, finding interdisciplinary connections. Graphical representation of information

contributes to the development of the ability to work with text, because it allows you to learn to formulate the main idea, highlight key words, divide the text into structural parts, collapse information in the form of secondary sources (plan, algorithm, table, diagram), expand it ("read" formulas, equations), recode from visual to verbal and vice versa. Develops all skills: listening, speaking, reading, writing. The use of this tool in education was proven in 2003. Institute for the Advancement of Research in Education (USA), which published a review of 29 studies on the use of visual teaching aids. Most of the studies focused specifically on graphic organizers. Scientists have found that their use improves student performance in several ways. Namely: Improves memorization of information - in the case when it is presented both visually and in textual form. Improves reading comprehension. Progress is growing, including for students with learning difficulties. Improves critical thinking skills. Practical part. The authors of the educational and methodological manual "Methods and means of organizing independent educational activities of students" B.Yu. Khodiev and L.V. Golish classify graphic organizers according to three criteria. 1. By methods and means of structuring information, establishing links and relationships between the concepts studied: cluster, mental maps, "Insert" table, categorical and conceptual tables, denotative graph. 2. By methods and means of analysis, comparison of information: "T" scheme, Venn diagram. "Why?", "Fish Skeleton", "Lotus Flower" schemes, "How?" hierarchical diagram, SWOT analysis. Common graphic organizers, the use of which is accessible and convenient in the study of the Russian language and literature, include: Venn, Lotus Flower, Denotative Graph, Fishbone, T Chart, and Concept Table. System Organizers. This view includes timelines, schematic algorithms, cyclic diagrams. Some of them can be used to describe the historical or biographical sequence of events, the actions of the main characters. These include organizers Ladder, Chain of events, Clock, Cycles (in case of cyclical events). Thus, practice proves the expediency of using graphic organizers. This is especially true in the transition to the updated content of education, in which great importance is attached to instilling in students the skills of critical thinking, research, communication, the ability to solve problems and creatively apply knowledge, work in a group. In order to choose the right scheme for working with material, you need to know: the material covers only one topic or several how complex is the topic information linear or cyclic are there differences and similarities, facts "for" and "against" does the material contain dates, are there hierarchical levels. Graphic schemes are used: when presenting new material to comprehend and consolidate the

material being studied when summarizing and systematizing the studied material at the stage of controlling knowledge, skills and abilities assigned by the student of new knowledge; draw conclusions and summarize in the process of reflection. There is a huge variety of graphic organizers (tables, trees, clusters, mental maps, etc.), but they all play a significant role in the process of formative assessment in the classroom. With their help, you can check how students can compare information, concepts on several aspects; establish causal relationships. How they can reveal new concepts, write down key ideas. Graphic organizers are indispensable when working with a new theme, with text. They also provide invaluable assistance in constructing an oral or written statement, when the student composes an answer algorithm that includes key information, on the basis of which he subsequently builds his answer. which increases the internal motivation of schoolchildren to study the subject and interest in cognitive activity, independent search, develops teamwork skills, public speaking skills with the provision of evidence and arguments, the ability to think logically, opens up scope for the development of research skills. Each teacher chooses the methods that are more suitable for him, which he uses in the lessons of the language and literature. Active techniques and teaching methods contribute to: realization of the objectives of the lesson; activation of mental activity; development of critical thinking; Formation of functional literacy of students. Most importantly, the teacher must understand that the use of active methods and forms of work determines the approach to the content and development of the modern developing educational environment, increasing the motivation of students in the learning process, because students must not only "get" knowledge, but master the methods of cognition, that is, learn study.

Literature:

1. Antonova E.S. Methods of teaching the Russian language: a communicative activity approach: a textbook for university students / E.S. Antonova. - M.: KnoRUS, 2007. - 460 p.
2. Babenko L.G. Lexicology of the Russian language. Textbook / L.G. Babenko. - Yekaterinburg, 2008. -126 p.
3. Litnevskaya E.I. Methods of teaching the Russian language in secondary school: Educational allowance / Ed. E.I. Litnevskaya. - M.: Academic project, 2006. - 590 p.
4. Nelina G.A. Aspects of teaching the Russian language in a modern school / G.A. Nelina. -Nikolaev: OIPPO, 2011. -140 p.

5. Teacher's guide. The educational program of advanced training courses for teaching staff in the subjects "Russian language" and "Russian literature" in schools with a non-Russian language of instruction. -2016

